

NEUTRON DIFFRACTION MEASUREMENT AND MODELLING OF STRESSES AROUND FATIGUE CRACKS IN Al/SiC_p COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The influence of quench-induced residual stresses on the fatigue crack growth rate in cyclic bending is analysed. Neutron diffraction measurements of the elastic strain fields ahead of a fatigue crack in an Al/SiC particulate composite and an unreinforced aluminium alloy specimens suggest that the crack tips remain held open even in unloaded samples. Within the framework of LEFM a theoretical model, based on the dislocation distribution technique, is used to investigate the point of closure, to find the values of stress intensity factors at the crack tip, and to predict the stresses ahead of the crack. Predictions are also compared with FEM simulation results.

1. INTRODUCTION

Particulate metal matrix composites (MMCs) based on aluminium alloys offer great increases in specific strength and stiffness over the unreinforced alloys. Potential applications where considerable weight savings may be achieved include aircraft structures and automotive components. One of the aspects restricting further progress in this field is a lower fatigue resistance of these materials compared to the base alloys. The fact that particulate composites are highly inhomogeneous on the microstructural level makes accurate application of the standard methods of linear elastic fracture mechanics to these materials difficult. However, even within the framework of LEFM, more reliable methods for fatigue life prediction of composite structures need to be developed.

Al/SiC composites are commonly based on precipitation hardened commercial alloys, e.g. such as 2124 or 8090. During fabrication most alloys undergo thermal processing aimed at optimising their microstructure and achieving the required properties. A typical heat treatment comprises solution treatment at a temperature of around 770 K, followed by water quenching and an ageing treatment. Such thermal treatment is known to produce a distribution of residual stresses within the material, ranging from the microscopic to long-range macroscopic [1].

Residual microstresses in metal matrix composites may arise due to the mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficients, stiffness or plasticity between the two phases. These stresses vary over relatively small distances, comparable to the spacing of the reinforcing particles (~10 μm) [1]. However, while they must average to zero over larger distances, they usually have a finite mean value in each phase. For example, upon cooling from the processing temperature tensile mean stresses develop in the Al alloy matrix and compressive stresses in the SiC particles. Macroscopic residual stresses, on the other hand, are long range stresses, varying over distances of the order of ≥1mm. These stresses may arise both in composite and homogeneous materials due to non-uniform plastic deformation, as in shot-peening, or due to the difference in the cooling rates experienced by the outlying surface layer with respect to the core regions, when the material is quenched.

Although microstresses undoubtedly play an important role in governing the processes at the tip of a fatigue crack, their influence on the growth rate may often be assumed to be uniform throughout

the sample. Bearing this in mind, we concentrate our attention on the interaction between the growing fatigue crack and its associated crack tip stress field, and the macroscopic residual stresses. Macro stresses are known to lead to crack front bowing [2] if they vary across the crack front, or to the effects of crack closure and crack tip shielding, when the residual stresses vary along the crack path [3].

In cyclic loading of a residual stress-free fatigue sample, e.g. a compact tension or standard edge-notched bending specimen, according to the solution given by the elasticity theory the opposite faces of the crack come into contact, and separate again, over the crack's full length at precisely zero load. However, since the discovery of plasticity-induced crack closure by Elber [4] in the early 1960's, a variety of mechanisms have been put forward and discussed [5] which lead to premature contact of crack faces over some part of their length during unloading, at non-zero loads. This effect leads to a variation in the effective stress intensity factor range $\Delta K_{eff} = K_{max,eff} - K_{min,eff}$, experienced by the crack tip, thus modifying the apparent fatigue resistance. The presence of residual stresses may also cause crack closure at non-zero loads. In particular, residual stresses may force the crack to start closing from a point located a large distance behind the crack front, rather than from the tip. Such behaviour has been observed before under different conditions (e.g. following a large plastic overload [6]), and is termed *discontinuous crack closure*. It may lead to the crack remaining open in the vicinity of the tip even in a fully unloaded sample. If this indeed takes place, the actual value of $K_{min,eff}$ at the crack tip is increased to a higher value, and ΔK_{eff} is reduced, leading to crack growth retardation.

Experimentally, the occurrence of closure may be deduced from measurements of the crack growth rate and the specimen compliance [7]. An alternative technique, neutron diffraction, provides a unique capability of probing stresses inside the material non-destructively, with resolution down to 0.5 mm [3]. Using this technique, it is possible to measure the elastic strains in front of the crack tip in unloaded or loaded samples. Thus information on the precise nature of loading experienced by the crack tip at each stage of the fatigue cycle may be obtained, and conclusions may be drawn about the mode of crack closure and the amount of shielding taking place.

In this paper, a body of experimental data obtained using neutron diffraction is analysed showing crack tip stress fields of fatigue cracks in loaded and unloaded residually-stressed samples. From this analysis it is clear that crack closure is operating. Correct interpretation of crack growth experiments requires a knowledge of the fatigue crack extension driving force, ΔK_{eff} , for each value of crack length. In order to establish whether discontinuous crack closure can account for the observed variation in crack growth rates, it is necessary to be able to predict theoretically the extent of crack closure and the actual stress intensity factor range from a given geometry, loading conditions and the knowledge of the residual stress field. Two theoretical approaches are used in order to model this effect, namely, the finite-element method and the dislocation distribution technique. Predictions made using these models are compared, and their relative advantages and shortcomings are evaluated.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The materials used in this study were unreinforced aluminium alloy 2124, as well as the same alloy reinforced with 20 wt% of particulate SiC, nominally of 3 μm diameter. They were produced by Aerospace Metal Composites, Farnborough, UK, by a powder metallurgy route, involving hot isostatic pressing at $\sim 500^\circ\text{C}$, followed by slow cooling. The alloy was subsequently forged and extruded to a final plate thickness of ~ 13 mm, whereas the reinforced billet was hot forged and rolled to a plate of thickness of ~ 15 mm.

Figure 1. Plate and specimen configuration and axes.

The materials were solution treated at 505°C in plate form and subsequently quenched into cold water. Single edge-notched bend (SENB) specimens were cut from the plate in the T-S orientation, according to the diagram shown in Figure 1. The samples were machined evenly on both sides down to the thicknesses of 12.5 mm and 14 mm for the unreinforced alloy and the composite respectively. They were examined either in the naturally-aged (NA) condition, or overaged (OA) for 48 hours at 180°C in order to reduce the level of the residual stresses due to quenching. Two samples were analysed in the course of this study, a composite sample in the overaged condition and an alloy sample, which was naturally aged and then overaged.

Fatigue tests were performed on a 100 kN Mayes servo-hydraulic testing machine, in 4-point bending with an inner span of 20 mm and a sinusoidal applied loading cycle of frequency 20 Hz (following ASTM test standard E647 recommendations). Fatigue cracks were grown in the samples to the lengths of 8.12 mm for the reinforced sample, and 7.54 mm for the alloy sample.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The neutron scattering experiments were carried out on the L3 spectrometer of the NRU reactor at Chalk River, Canada [1]. The sample was mounted in a 4-point bending rig, so that a bending moment could be applied to the sample while it was *in situ* on the diffractometer, and the state of stress in the vicinity of the crack tip could be measured both in the loaded and unloaded state. A neutron wavelength of $2.4330 \pm 0.0001 \text{ \AA}$ was used, which was produced by reflection from a Ge single crystal monochromator. NIST Si powder standard was used for calibration. The lattice strain component ϵ_y was measured using Al (111) and (200) reflections at scattering angles 2θ of 62.7° and 73.9° respectively, and the SiC (111) reflections at $2\theta = 57.9^\circ$. On the initial stages of the experiment it was determined that the strains from Al (111) and (200) planes were in close agreement, and only Al(111) reflections were used for the majority of subsequent measurements for intensity reasons.

Figure 2(a). Elastic strain (ϵ_y) measured along a line parallel, but 8 mm away, from the crack: ■ loaded, ◇ unloaded, -- parabolic fit, * difference

Figure 2(b). Elastic strain along the crack line in the crack opening direction in the NA alloy bar

The elastic strain distributions in the crack opening direction (ϵ_y) as a function of the coordinate z through the plate, measured along a line parallel to but 8 mm away from the crack, are shown in Figure 2(a) for the NA bar. In the unloaded case, the strain variation is very well described by a parabola. A slight deviation from stress balance may be noted (of about 400 microstrain, $\mu\epsilon$, in the tensile direction), which is probably due to inaccuracy in the measurement of the stress free lattice parameter d_0 . On the whole, these measurements confirm that the quench residual stress in the sample may be accurately described by a parabolic distribution, with a surface (maximum) compressive stress of around 200 MPa for the naturally aged alloy bar.

The elastic strains in the crack opening direction were then measured on the crack plane, and are shown in Figure 2(b) for the same specimen, both for the loaded and unloaded cases. At $K_{max,app}$, the expected peak is observed in the elastic strain ϵ_y , associated with the presence of the crack tip. Its position corresponds with good accuracy to the actual crack front location of 7.54 mm, observed when the specimen was subsequently broken. From the comparison of the stresses measured for the loaded and unloaded cases it is clear that while the stresses at the tip and

at the back face become less tensile and less compressive respectively, upon unloading, there remains a considerable bending moment within the uncracked ligament, despite the absence of externally applied forces. This observation leads us to the conclusion that the state of stress experienced by the crack front in both cases is very similar and only a variation in its intensity is noted. This situation may only arise if the crack is held open at the tip throughout the fatigue cycle, even for $K_{min,app} = 0$, and suggests that crack closure is taking place. The neutron results suggest that the crack first starts to close from the notch.

Figure 3(a). Lattice strain (ϵ_y) on the crack plane in the matrix.

Figure 3(b). Lattice strain (ϵ_y) on the crack plane in SiC

The assumption that closure is operating is corroborated by the results on the composite material. In Figures 3(a) and 3(b), the elastic strain components ϵ_y in the matrix and the reinforcement for the overaged composite bar are shown, and the same pattern is clearly visible. Several other important features should be noted. Firstly, the effect of the thermal mismatch stresses is clearly seen. From Figure 3 the far field matrix strains are tensile, while those in the particles are compressive, elevating or depressing the parabolae respectively. The mismatch term is equivalent to a temperature drop of around 230°C [3]. As a result, over the 0.5 mm sampling length, the elastic strains in the particles are compressive everywhere, even near the crack tip.

Figure 4. Load:displacement plot showing the points of opening and closure

In summary, the neutron results strongly indicate that crack closure is occurring. This would seem to be confirmed by crack compliance measurements of closure in the NA and OA composites., Points K_{cl} and K_{op} in Figure 4 correspond to the levels of applied K when a deviation from the linear relationship between the applied load and the displacement is first observed. From Figures 5(a,b), which show the variation of the measured K_{cl} and K_{op} with the crack length, it is clear that the level of closure is much higher in the more residually stressed NA material. It is also interesting to note that for the NA material K_{cl} and K_{op} diverge with the increasing crack length. This is almost certainly due to an increase in the portion of the unloading curve over which the crack

progressively closes as the crack length grows. This effect has been observed recently and has been ascribed to discontinuous crack closure [8]. In order to examine the possibility of discontinuous crack closure in this case it is necessary to understand via modelling how the quench stress field might affect the crack behaviour.

Figure 5(a). Crack closure level measurement results for NA composite bar.

Figure 5(b). Crack closure level measurement results for OA composite bar.

4. THEORETICAL MODELS

Two approaches have been used to determine the extent of discontinuous crack closure induced by the parabolic residual stress distribution due to quenching, the finite-element method and the singular integral equation method.

4.1. FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

Loading of the residually stressed sample in bending was modelled using the finite element package ABAQUS on a Silicon Graphics workstation. Since the variation of residual stresses across the sample is relatively smooth, a fairly coarse mesh may be employed in order to model the crack opening. A focused mesh consisting of quarter-point eight-node quadratic elements is used in order to model the crack tip, as shown in Figure 6. The J -integral method, which is implemented in the standard ABAQUS package, is used to evaluate the stress intensity factor at the crack tip. As the result provided by this method depends on the path encircling the crack tip chosen to evaluate the integral, further mesh refinement is required in order to obtain more accurate values.

Figure 6. A coarse finite element mesh, showing the effect of quench residual stress on the crack opening profile, and crack contact occurring in the vicinity of the crack mouth.

In the course of this study the main motivation consisted of establishing the degree of crack face contact, as the stress intensity factors may be evaluated with greater efficiency and speed using the integral equation technique described below [9]. In order to model the residual stresses, a special feature in ABAQUS is employed which allows the initial stress distribution to be prescribed at all nodal points via a user subroutine. In the case of quench stresses a parabolic function of the z -coordinate shown in Figure 2(a) gives the values of direct stress in the crack opening direction. Bending moment, applied to the specimen in 4-point bending configuration, is modelled by a linear distribution of normal stresses along the edge of the specimen. Due to the symmetry of the problem it suffices to model only half of the specimen. Horizontal displacement of the points ahead of the crack, lying on the axis of symmetry, is restricted, whereas the crack face is allowed to move leading to crack opening. In order to model closure, a rigid surface must be introduced along the axis of symmetry, preventing the crack faces from interpenetration. The amount of closure is determined by the length of crack face that has come into contact with the rigid surface.

4.2. SINGULAR INTEGRAL EQUATION TECHNIQUE

The singular integral equation technique, or the dislocation density method as it is known in application to crack problems, relies on the fact that any problem about a crack may be formulated as a boundary value problem in the theory of elasticity; where the conditions along a part of the boundary occupied by the crack are given in terms of the displacement jump, rather than its value for each side of the crack. By varying this unknown crack opening displacement (COD), it is possible to find the precise shape to which the crack opens under the applied loading. The relationship between the unknown crack profile and the stress existing along the crack line in the crack's absence is written in the form of an integral equation. The kernel of this equation $K(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{r})$, i.e. the function giving the value of stress at an observation point \mathbf{r} within the material due to the crack opening at the source point \mathbf{s} , corresponds to the overall geometry of a particular problem. The exact expressions for $K(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{r})$ for an infinite elastic plane, an elastic half-plane or a infinite strip of material are available in the literature [9-11].

The crucial point in the dislocation density modelling is the correct representation of the crack opening displacement behaviour as the crack tip or the point of crack face contact is approached. It is known from the basics of linear elastic fracture mechanics that at the tip the crack opens by an amount proportional to the root of the distance from the tip. The proportionality coefficient relates to the stress intensity factor. Thus, if the correct variation of the crack opening is assumed in the model, the stress intensity factor may be readily abstracted from the solution. By the same token, from the fundamentals of elasticity it is known that the distribution of stress in the vicinity of a smooth contact is also proportional to the root of distance, and, correspondingly, the separation of the two initially straight touching surfaces is proportional to $r^{3/2}$. Full mathematical background of this class of problem is presented in great detail in the book by Muskhelishvili [12]. To effect the solution, the unknown crack opening displacement may be expressed as a product of a fundamental, or weight function, prescribing the correct behaviour at the interval ends, and an unknown smooth function, which may be determined with great accuracy in the course of analysis.

One of the great advantages of this method lies in the fact that it is solely the one-dimensional distribution function on the interval corresponding to the crack location that needs to be determined. The time of preparation is greatly reduced, and the solution takes only a few seconds on a modern desktop computer. Modelling crack closure introduces an additional complication in that the exact location of the first point of contact is not known *a priori* and needs to be found iteratively in the course of solution. However, very few iterations (5-10) are sufficient in order to establish this additional unknown parameter, and the time required is still on the order of seconds.

Once the unknown distribution function has been found, the stresses and displacements at an arbitrary point within the domain may be evaluated using a single quadrature. The level of accuracy with which they are determined is uniform throughout the domain, as no interpolation is involved, in contrast with the FEM.

Comparison of the results obtained using the dislocation density technique with those from finite element simulations confirmed that this technique provides a quick and effective method of modelling discontinuous crack closure, induced by the residual stresses. Although the results for the stress intensity factors provided by both methods were in very good agreement (under 5% error

for a suitably refined mesh used in FEM), the execution and especially the preparation time for the dislocation density method was considerably shorter.

4.3. MODELLING RESULTS

In Figure 7(a), the result obtained using the dislocation density model is shown. The stress variation along the line of the crack (solid line), with closure occurring near the notch, is plotted along the crack line, together with the crack opening profile (long dash). Note the peak associated with the stress intensification near the tip and the compressive stress developing in the area of contact. Note also that the effect of closure is to maintain a tensile stress at the crack tip on unloading, in agreement with the neutron observations. The compressive stress at the crack mouth is outside the range of neutron measurements. It is also worth noting that the crack opening displacements are small and that plasticity and debris-related closure mechanisms will also operate.

Figure 7(a). Stress distribution on the crack plane in a fully unloaded sample

Figure 7(b). Variation of K_{app} and K_{eff} during the unloading half of the fatigue cycle.

It is interesting to consider the variation of the effective stress intensity factor range ΔK_{eff} which is experienced by the crack tip during a typical fatigue cycle. In the case of an overaged alloy bar, the applied stress intensity factor range used was $\Delta K_{app}=17 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$, with the load ratio of $R=0.1$. In Figure 7(b) a comparison is made between the variation of the applied stress intensity factor, deduced from the specimen configuration and loading disregarding the presence of the residual stresses, and the effective stress intensity factor, calculated assuming that discontinuous crack closure is taking place. Note that on the initial part of the unloading stage of the cycle, the value of ΔK_{eff} (and $K_{eff,max}$) is reduced primarily due to the action of the surface compressive residual stress, which tends to close the crack at the mouth and thus considerably reduce the opening load applied at the crack tip. At a certain time during the cycle, when K_{app} reaches a critical value ($K_{app}^* \approx 8 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ in this case), the first contact of crack faces takes place. Following this event, the crack remains held open near the tip by the combined action of the surface compressive residual stresses and the tensile residual stresses acting in the core region. The compressive residual stresses press the crack faces together near the mouth, which keep the rest of the crack propped open, restricting further closure. The tensile residual stresses in the core region act as an opening load in the near-tip region. Due to the combination of these effects further variation of K_{eff} is very slow. As a result, the value of $K_{eff,min}$ is increased considerably, and ΔK_{eff} is greatly reduced.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Neutron diffraction results indicate that while the magnitude of the crack tip stresses reduces as the applied K is reduced from K_{max} , they are significant even at $K_{app}=0$. The form of the stress field suggests that crack closure acts to hold the crack tip open, reducing ΔK_{eff} . Indeed, larger ΔK are required to drive cracks in the NA composite relative to the OA material for which the residual stresses have been reduced by a factor of two. This inference is corroborated by compliance methods for the examination of closure, which indicate a much higher level of closure for the

specimen in the NA state relative to the OA ones ($\Delta K \sim 10 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for NA cf. $\Delta K \sim 5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ for OA).

Two theoretical approaches were analysed, aimed at interpreting the results of the neutron diffraction stress measurements. These models suggest that the presence of quench-induced residual stresses is likely to result in discontinuous crack closure, with the first instance of crack face contact being well removed from the crack tip. While further refinements of the models described are required to include the effects of plasticity and more accurately to incorporate the influence of the notch, the results amply demonstrate the effect that residual stress induced closure can have on the ΔK experienced by an advancing crack. Further experimental work will focus on methods of identifying the location and progression of crack closure as the crack grows.

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